

Attractive Force in a Rotational Gravitational Field

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Am I sure that dark matter exists? Almost certainly.
Jim Al-Khalili

Abstract

Newton's law of gravitation is reconsidered in a new context, a rotational gravitational field is discussed, with the hypothesis of an "attractive force in a rotational gravitational field." It is argued that there is a difference between a gravitational field that rotates and one that does not. A "critical radius" R_C is introduced, connected to the speed of light through a relation $R_C = \frac{c}{\omega}$. . . It is assumed that the gravity within our galaxy consists of two gravitational fields: one caused by the mass of the rotating supermassive black hole at the center of our galaxy (SgrA*) and one caused by the mass of stars and other baryonic matter within the galaxy. Using this hypothesis, the rotation curve of our galaxy is successfully described without the need for the "dark matter" hypothesis.

Keywords: rotational gravitational field, critical radius, galaxy rotation curve, components of the gravitational field, dark matter, Newton's law of gravitation, supermassive black hole SgrA*

Introduction

Stars and other matter that make up a galaxy orbit around its center, whose dynamics are described by Newton's law of gravitation. Considering only the baryonic mass, it is expected that the rotational velocities of stars would continuously decrease with increasing distance from the galactic center, following $v \propto r^{-1/2}$ (Keplerian decline). However, observations have shown that the orbital velocities of stars are higher than expected and tend to remain roughly constant, indicating the presence of some influence that maintains these velocities. The galaxy's rotation curve is a graphical representation of the relationship between orbital velocity and distance from the center of gravity.

Figure 1. Rotation curve of a typical spiral galaxy
(<https://citizendium.org/wiki/images/3/31/GalaxyRotationCurve.png>)

The question arises: what affects the orbital velocities of baryonic matter in galaxies? One answer is the "dark matter hypothesis." Another answer is "MOND – Modified Newtonian Dynamics." A third answer is attempted in this work through the "hypothesis of the attractive force in a rotational gravitational field."

Attractive Force in a Rotational Gravitational Field

Certain limitations exist in the universe, one of which is the speed of light. This may be the hidden reason for the unexpected rotation curves of stars in spiral galaxies, i.e., it is embedded in all fundamental natural laws. In Newtonian theory, the effect of gravity is instantaneous. However, in special relativity, simultaneity loses meaning, and the effect of gravity propagates through space at the speed of light. If a body changes position in space, the gravitational force at any point in space changes according to this displacement only after the time it takes for information about the position change to travel at the speed of light. Therefore, the speed of gravity is equal to the speed of light, i.e., the causal speed, and is thus a key element of this hypothesis alongside mass and the angular velocity of the rotating mass. Another fundamental assumption of this hypothesis is that a rotating gravitational field is not identical to a non-rotating gravitational field.

The following graphical representation shows an object in a rotational gravitational field, where:

M – mass creating the gravitational field

m – mass of the object influenced by the gravitational field

ω – angular velocity of the gravitational field rotation

r – distance from the center of mass of M to the center of mass of m

φ – deviation of the object with mass of m from the equatorial plane of the rotating gravitational field

R_c – critical radius

c – speed of light

v – tangential velocity of the object in the gravitational field

Figure 2. Graphical representation of an object in a rotational gravitational field

Critical Radius:

$$v = \omega \cdot r \rightarrow R_c = \frac{c}{\omega}$$

Gravitational field regime within a cylinder of radius R_c :

$$r < \frac{R_c}{\cos\varphi} \rightarrow F = G \cdot \frac{M \cdot m}{r^2} \rightarrow v = \sqrt{\frac{G \cdot M}{r}}$$

$r < \frac{R_c}{\cos\varphi} \rightarrow$ The force in the gravitational field is inversely proportional to the square of the distance (inverse-square law).

Gravitational field regime outside a cylinder of radius R_c :

$$r > \frac{R_c}{\cos\varphi} \rightarrow F = G \cdot \frac{M \cdot m \cdot \cos\varphi}{R_c \cdot r} \rightarrow v = \sqrt{\frac{G \cdot M \cdot \cos\varphi}{R_c}} = \underline{\text{const. !!!}}$$

$r > \frac{R_c}{\cos\varphi} \rightarrow$ The force in the gravitational field is inversely proportional to the distance (inverse-square law no longer applies at distances greater than $\frac{R_c}{\cos\varphi}$).

An Explanation of Matter Rotation Velocities in Spiral Galaxies Consistent with the Proposed Hypothesis

Rotation curves of spiral galaxies, including the Milky Way, represent a fundamental problem in galactic dynamics. Observed orbital velocities of stars and gas remain approximately constant at large galactic radii, contrary to expectations from Newtonian gravity applied to visible (baryonic) mass. Standard approaches involve the existence of a massive dark matter halo, while alternative approaches include modifications of the gravitational law. Based on the observed tangential velocities of stars in spiral galaxies, it is noted that up to a certain radius from the galactic center, the inverse-square law holds, while beyond that radius, the force becomes inversely proportional to distance.

The gravitational field of a spiral galaxy can be described with two components: the gravitational field around a rotating supermassive black hole with an accretion disk, and the gravitational field caused by the mass of stars and other baryonic matter in the galaxy.

The gravitational field around the rotating supermassive black hole has a significant angular velocity, and its critical radius R_c is relatively small. The force of the gravitational field at a distance $r = \frac{R_c}{\cos\varphi}$ is inversely proportional to the distance r

$$F = G \cdot \frac{M \cdot m \cdot \cos\varphi}{R_c \cdot r}$$

and the inverse-square law does not apply. As a result, matter in this rotating gravitational field cannot rotate at speeds lower than

$$v = \sqrt{\frac{G \cdot M \cdot \cos\varphi}{R_c}}$$

where M – mass of the massive black hole with an accretion disk.

The gravitational field caused by the masses of matter in a galaxy (without a massive black hole with an accretion disk) has a relatively small angular rotation speed, and the critical radius R_c for this field is much larger than the radius of the galaxy itself. Consequently, the gravitational force within the galaxy is inversely proportional to the square of the distance (the inverse-square law). Therefore, in this field (up to a distance $r = \frac{R_c}{\cos\varphi}$ the classical Newtonian formula applies:

$$F = G \cdot \frac{M \cdot m}{r^2}$$

where M is the mass of the galaxy within radius r, excluding the black hole.

The synthesis of these hypothetical fields results in the dominance of the gravitational field from baryonic matter due to its much larger mass within the galactic disk, while the effect of the black hole's field becomes noticeable in the outer regions of spiral galaxies because it limits the minimum rotational speed of matter to

$$v_{min} = \sqrt{\frac{G \cdot M \cdot \cos\varphi}{R_c}}$$

where M – the mass of the massive black hole with an accretion disk.

Within the rotational gravitational field, a cylindrical region of diameter $2 \cdot R_c$ along the black hole's rotation axis exists, where the inverse-square law holds, creating a "gravitational underpressure" that may contribute to the formation of astrophysical jets.

Milky Way Rotation Curve Model

This chapter presents an intentionally unconventional but mathematically defined model examining whether the observed Milky Way rotation curve can be reproduced without dark matter, considering the central supermassive black hole properties:

- Mass of SgrA* is a compact, homogeneous mass with a spherical shape:

$$M(\text{SgrA}^*) = 8.26 \cdot 10^{36} \text{ kg}$$

- Rotation period of SgrA*:

$$T = 13 \text{ years} = 4.04352 \cdot 10^8 \text{ s} \rightarrow \omega = \frac{2\pi}{T} = 1.5531 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ rad/s}$$

Structure of the model: The total rotational velocity of stars is modeled as the quadratic sum of contributions from three baryonic components:

1. Central supermassive black hole SgrA*
2. Central galactic bulge
3. Galactic disk

Circular orbits satisfy:

$$v_{model} = \sqrt{v_{BH}^2(r) + v_{bulge}^2(r) + v_{disc}^2(r)}$$

where r is the distance from the center of the galaxy.

Contribution of the black hole Sgr A* under the following assumptions:

- Mass of SgrA* is a compact, homogeneous mass with a spherical shape:

$$M_{BH} = 8.26 \cdot 10^{36} \text{ kg}$$

- Rotation period of SgrA*:

$$T = 13 \text{ years} = 4.04352 \cdot 10^8 \text{ s} \rightarrow \omega = \frac{2\pi}{T} = 1.5531 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ rad/s}$$

The limiting radius R_c of the rotational gravitational field around SgrA* is given by:

$$R_c = \frac{c}{\omega} = \frac{3 \cdot 10^8 \text{ m/s}}{1.5531 \cdot 10^{-8} / \text{s}} = 1.93162 \cdot 10^{16} \text{ m} = 0.626 \text{ pc}$$

At distances smaller than the critical radius $R_c = 0.626 \text{ pc}$, the orbital velocity follows the standard Keplerian law:

$$v_{BH} = \sqrt{\frac{G \cdot M_{BH}}{r}}, \quad r < R_c$$

At the critical radius, the velocity equals:

$$v_{BH} = \sqrt{\frac{G \cdot M_{BH}}{R_c}} \approx 172 \text{ km/s}, \quad r > R_c$$

Beyond this radius, the black hole contribution remains constant and equals 172 km/s.

Contribution of the galactic bulge:

The central bulge is modeled with a spherically symmetric Hernquist mass profile:

$$\rho(r) = \frac{M_{bulge}}{2\pi} \cdot \frac{a}{r(r+a)^3}$$

with parameters:

$$M_{bulge} = 1.65 \times 10^{10} M_{\odot}$$

$$a = 0.522 \text{ kpc}$$

The resulting orbital velocity is:

$$v_{bulge}^2(r) = \frac{G \cdot M_{bulge} \cdot r}{(r+a)^2}$$

The bulge dominates the inner regions of the galaxy within a few kiloparsecs from the center, and its contribution decreases with radius.

Contribution of the galactic disk:

The disk is described as a thin exponential disk with a surface density:

$$\Sigma(r) = \Sigma_0 e^{-r/r_d}$$

with parameters:

$$M_{disk} = 3.41 \times 10^{10} M_{\odot}$$

$$R_d = 2.6 \text{ kpc}$$

The central density is:

$$\Sigma_0 = \frac{M_{disc}}{2\pi r_d^2}$$

the orbital velocity is calculated using Freeman's formula:

$$v_{disc}^2(r) = 4\pi G \Sigma_0 R_d y^2 [I_0(y)K_0(y) - I_1(y)K_1(y)], \quad y = \frac{r}{2r_d}$$

where I_n i K_n are the modified Bessel functions.

Comparison with observations:

Model applied to the Milky Way and compared with the "grand rotation curve" (Sofue 2011).

Table 1 shows rotation velocities from individual contributions and observed values with deviations

r [kpc]	v_{BH} [km/s]	v_{bulge} [km/s]	v_{disk} [km/s]	v_{model} [km/s]	v_{obs} [km/s]	Δv [km/s]
0.01	172	50	2	179	180	-1
0.1	172	135	12	219	210	9
0.5	172	163	38	240	220	20
1	172	134	64	227	220	7
2.2	172	94	126	232	225	7
4	172	68	163	246	230	16
8	172	88	141	239	220	19
15	172	67	107	213	220	-7
25	172	52	79	196	220	-24

Table 1.

The results show that the model reproduces a nearly flat rotation curve between ~ 1 and ~ 25 kpc, with deviations on the order of ± 20 km/s, which are comparable to observational uncertainties.

Figure 3. Milky Way rotation curve

The observed velocities (Sofue 2011) and the total velocity obtained by the considered model without dark matter are shown. As visible in Figure 3, the model without dark matter successfully reproduces the shape of the observed rotation curve of the Milky Way.

Conclusion

„The Hypothesis of a Rotational Gravitational Field” successfully describes the dynamics of baryonic matter in spiral galaxies, without the need for a dark matter hypothesis, as shown by the Milky Way rotation curve. The goal is not to assert the physical reality of this model, but to quantitatively demonstrate that it can mimic the effect of dark matter.

If a rotating gravitational field indeed acts differently on its surroundings than a non-rotating field, which requires further scientific investigation, this work and the "rotational gravitational field hypothesis" open up an interesting set of issues worthy of further consideration.

For example, galaxies such as NGC 1052–DF2, NGC 1052–DF4, FFC 224, and NGC 1277 appear devoid of dark matter, which, in this hypothesis, implies that the critical radius R_C (if present) lies beyond the visible galaxy.

Varaždin, December 2025.

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